

IoT Fuelling Analytics

Aliasgher Dalal^a

^a

Abstract

The explosive growth in IoT promises radical changes in technology landscape with an economic impact predicted to be in trillions in the coming decade. One of the beneficiaries of IoT is likely Analytics i.e. AI and Machine Learning. Analytics will benefit from the IoT because its a catalyst to creation of large amounts of data. Data that comes from monitoring various industrial, consumer and other sectors of economy. Data is fuel to analytics, without data analytics is car with an empty tank. My talk today addresses data generated by IoT and its implications on AI, and in turn to global economy at large.

May 9, 2019